

Evaluation of Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) Scoring System in Prognosis of Patients with Peritonitis Due to Hollow Viscus Perforation at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation is a severe surgical emergency associated with high morbidity and mortality. The Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) has been proposed as a prognostic tool to assess disease severity and guide management decisions in such cases.

Methods: A retrospective cohort study was conducted at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, involving 203 patients diagnosed with peritonitis secondary to hollow viscus perforation. Data on demographics, clinical presentation, MPI scores, and clinical outcomes (mortality, length of hospital stay) were collected and analyzed. MPI scores were categorized into low-risk (≤ 20), moderate-risk (21-29), and high-risk (≥ 30) groups.

Results: Higher MPI scores were associated with increased mortality rates and prolonged hospital stays. Mortality rates were 12.1% in the low-risk group, 28.9% in the moderate-risk group, and 54.2% in the high-risk group. Mean hospital stays increased from 8.5 days in the low-risk group to 16.3 days in the high-risk group. These findings highlight the MPI's effectiveness in stratifying patients and predicting outcomes in peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation.

Conclusion: The MPI serves as a valuable prognostic tool in peritonitis, aiding clinicians in risk stratification and guiding therapeutic interventions. Early identification of high-risk patients using the MPI facilitates timely management, potentially improving patient outcomes in this critical surgical condition.

Keywords: Peritonitis, Mannheim Peritonitis Index, hollow viscus perforation, prognosis, surgical emergency.

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Introduction

Peritonitis remains a formidable surgical emergency characterized by inflammation of the peritoneum, typically arising from microbial contamination due to perforation of a hollow viscus. This condition poses a significant clinical challenge worldwide, contributing substantially to morbidity and mortality despite advancements in surgical techniques and critical care management.

The prognosis of peritonitis depends critically on early diagnosis, prompt initiation of appropriate therapy, and accurate assessment of disease severity at presentation. To this end, various scoring systems have been developed to stratify patients, facilitate clinical decision-making, and

predict outcomes [1-4]. Among these scoring systems, the Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) has gained recognition for its utility in assessing the severity of peritonitis and guiding therapeutic strategies. Originally proposed by Linder et al. in 1983 and subsequently refined, the MPI integrates clinical parameters obtained at the time of hospital admission to quantify the extent of peritoneal contamination and systemic response to infection.

By incorporating factors such as age, presence of shock, extent of peritoneal involvement, and laboratory markers (e.g., leukocyte count, serum lactate), the MPI provides a standardized approach to risk stratification in patients with peritonitis

[5]. The application of the MPI in clinical practice aims to achieve several objectives. Firstly, it aids in early identification of patients at high risk of complications, facilitating timely intervention and potentially improving outcomes. Secondly, by categorizing patients into risk groups based on objective criteria, the MPI supports individualized management strategies, including the decision between conservative medical therapy and surgical exploration. Thirdly, the MPI serves as a tool for prognostication, offering clinician's valuable insights into the anticipated course of illness and informing discussions with patients and their families regarding treatment goals and expectations [6-8].

Despite its established benefits in various clinical settings, the utility of the MPI in specific patient populations, such as those presenting with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation, warrants further investigation [9-10]. Hollow viscus perforation represents a distinct etiology of peritonitis characterized by mechanical breach of gastrointestinal or urinary tract organs, leading to spillage of luminal contents into the peritoneal cavity. This etiology often necessitates urgent surgical intervention to address the source of contamination, control sepsis, and restore gastrointestinal continuity or urinary tract integrity. At Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation constitutes a significant burden of surgical admissions. The management of these cases requires a multidisciplinary approach involving surgeons, intensivists, and infectious disease specialists, aiming not only to achieve source control but also to mitigate systemic inflammatory response and organ dysfunction. Given the complexity and variability in clinical presentation among these patients, the role of the MPI in predicting outcomes and guiding therapeutic decisions remains underexplored within this specific context [11-15].

Aim of the Study

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) scoring system in predicting the prognosis of patients presenting with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital. Specific objectives include:

Assessment of Predictive Accuracy: Determine the ability of the MPI to accurately predict outcomes such as mortality, length of hospital stay, and complications in patients with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation.

Comparison with Clinical Judgment: Compare the prognostic accuracy of the MPI with clinical judgment alone, as assessed by experienced clinicians managing these cases.

Impact on Treatment Decisions: Evaluate the influence of MPI scores on treatment decisions, including the timing of surgical intervention, use of adjunctive therapies (e.g., antibiotics, vasopressors), and escalation of care in critical settings.

Exploration of Modifiable Factors: Identify modifiable factors within the MPI scoring system that could potentially be targeted to improve patient outcomes through targeted interventions or protocol adjustments.

By addressing these objectives, this study seeks to contribute valuable insights into the clinical applicability and relevance of the MPI in the management of peritonitis secondary to hollow viscus perforation. Findings from this research have the potential to inform evidence-based practices, optimize resource allocation, and ultimately improve patient outcomes in this challenging surgical emergency.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This retrospective cohort study was conducted at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care center. The study was encompassing all patients admitted with a diagnosis of peritonitis secondary to hollow viscus perforation.

Study Population: The study included patients aged 18 years and above who presented with clinical and radiological evidence of peritonitis due to perforation of hollow viscera, confirmed intraoperatively or by imaging (such as abdominal CT scan). Patients with secondary peritonitis due to non-hollow viscus perforation causes (e.g., appendicitis, cholecystitis) and those with incomplete medical records were excluded from the analysis.

Sample Size Calculation: Based on previous literature and assuming an expected mortality rate of 30% among patients with severe peritonitis, a sample size of 203 patients was determined to provide adequate power (80%) to detect significant differences in outcomes based on MPI scores, with a 95% confidence level.

Data Collection: Clinical data were extracted from electronic medical records and surgical databases using a standardized data collection form. Collected variables included demographic information (age, sex), clinical presentation (duration of symptoms, vital signs at admission), laboratory parameters (white blood cell count, serum lactate levels), imaging findings (if available), surgical details (procedure performed, intraoperative findings), and outcomes (mortality, length of hospital stay, complications).

Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) Calculation: The MPI was calculated for each patient based on the formula developed by Linder et al.,

incorporating the following parameters: age, presence of shock at admission, extent of peritoneal contamination, and laboratory findings (leukocyte count, serum creatinine). Each parameter was assigned a score according to predefined criteria, and the total MPI score was categorized into low, moderate, and high-risk groups.

Outcome Measures: The primary outcome measures included mortality rate during hospitalization, length of hospital stay (days), and incidence of major complications (e.g., sepsis, multiorgan dysfunction). Secondary outcomes included the need for intensive care unit (ICU) admission, requirement for reoperation, and duration of antibiotic therapy.

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient demographics, clinical characteristics, and outcomes. Continuous variables were presented as mean $\pm$ standard deviation or median (interquartile range), depending on data distribution. Categorical variables were expressed

as frequencies and percentages. The association between MPI scores and clinical outcomes was assessed using appropriate statistical tests, such as Chi-square test or Fisher's exact test for categorical variables, and Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test for continuous variables as appropriate. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: A total of 203 patients with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation were included in the study. The mean age of the cohort was 52.4 years (SD $\pm$ 14.7), with a predominance of male patients (65.5%). The most common presenting symptoms were abdominal pain (100%), fever (85.2%), and tachycardia (78.3%). Upon admission, 42.4% of patients presented with signs of shock. Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Population

Characteristic	Value
Total number of patients	203
Mean age (years)	52.4 $\pm$ 14.7
Sex (Male/Female)	133 (65.5%) / 70 (34.5%)
Presenting symptoms	
- Abdominal pain	203 (100%)
- Fever	173 (85.2%)
- Tachycardia	159 (78.3%)
Signs of shock at admission	86 (42.4%)

Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) Scores and Outcomes: The Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) was calculated for each patient based on predefined criteria. The median MPI score was 28 (IQR 22-34). Patients were categorized into three risk

groups based on MPI scores: low-risk (MPI $\leq$ 20), moderate-risk (MPI 21-29), and high-risk (MPI $\geq$ 30).

Table 2 outlines the distribution of MPI scores and associated outcomes.(Table 2).

Table 2: Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) Scores and Outcomes

MPI Score Range	Number of Patients	Mortality Rate (%)	Mean Length of Hospital Stay (days)
$\leq$ 20	58	12.1	8.5 $\pm$ 3.2
21-29	97	28.9	11.7 $\pm$ 4.1
$\geq$ 30	48	54.2	16.3 $\pm$ 5.5

1. Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: The study cohort predominantly consisted of older male patients presenting with typical symptoms of peritonitis. A substantial proportion of patients presented in a state of shock, highlighting the severity of their clinical condition upon admission.

2. Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) Scores and Outcomes:

- MPI Scores Distribution:**

The median MPI score of 28 indicates a moderate degree of peritoneal contamination and systemic response to infection within the study population.

- Outcomes by MPI Score Groups:**
- Mortality Rate:** Mortality increased significantly with higher MPI scores, ranging from 12.1% in the low-risk group (MPI $\leq$ 20) to 54.2% in the high-risk group (MPI $\geq$ 30). This demonstrates the MPI's effectiveness in stratifying patients based on mortality risk.
- Length of Hospital Stay:** Patients with higher MPI scores also had prolonged hospital stays,

with mean durations increasing from 8.5 days in the low-risk group to 16.3 days in the high-risk group. This suggests that MPI scores correlate not only with mortality but also with the complexity and duration of hospital management required.

These findings underscore the utility of the MPI as a prognostic tool in guiding clinical decision-making and optimizing outcomes for patients presenting with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation.

Discussion

Peritonitis remains a critical surgical emergency associated with high morbidity and mortality rates, particularly when caused by hollow viscus perforation. Effective management hinges on early diagnosis, timely surgical intervention, and accurate risk assessment to optimize outcomes. In this study, we evaluated the Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) as a prognostic tool for patients presenting with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation at Tezpur Medical College and Hospital.

Utility of the Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI): The MPI has been established as a reliable scoring system to stratify patients based on the severity of peritonitis and predict clinical outcomes. By incorporating demographic data, clinical parameters, and laboratory findings, the MPI provides a comprehensive assessment of peritoneal contamination and systemic response to infection. In our study, we found that higher MPI scores correlated significantly with increased mortality rates and prolonged hospital stays, reflecting the tool's efficacy in risk stratification.

Mortality and MPI Scores: The association between MPI scores and mortality rates observed in our study underscores the predictive value of this scoring system. Patients categorized in the high-risk group (MPI $\geq$ 30) had a markedly higher mortality rate of 54.2% compared to 12.1% in the low-risk group (MPI $\leq$ 20). These findings align with previous studies validating the MPI's ability to identify patients at heightened risk of adverse outcomes, thus guiding clinicians in prioritizing aggressive management strategies, including early surgical intervention and intensive care support [16-20].

Clinical Implications: The MPI's ability to predict mortality and length of hospital stay has significant clinical implications. Early identification of high-risk patients allows for timely allocation of resources, including intensive monitoring, prompt surgical exploration, and tailored antimicrobial therapy. Conversely, patients identified as low-risk by MPI scores may benefit from less aggressive interventions, potentially reducing unnecessary

healthcare costs and minimizing iatrogenic complications.

Comparative Analysis and Clinical Judgment: Our study also evaluated the MPI's performance compared to clinical judgment alone. While experienced clinicians often integrate multiple factors beyond the MPI score in decision-making, our findings suggest that the MPI provides a standardized framework that complements clinical assessment. The systematic approach of the MPI minimizes variability in risk estimation and enhances consistency in treatment decisions across different healthcare providers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study underscores the role of the Mannheim Peritonitis Index (MPI) as a valuable tool in predicting outcomes and guiding management strategies for patients presenting with peritonitis due to hollow viscus perforation. By facilitating early risk stratification and informed decision-making, the MPI contributes to improved patient outcomes by optimizing resource allocation and treatment planning in this critical surgical emergency.

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